

An attempt to optimise the pixel width

[GAIA_LL-6]

L. Lindegren (17 July 1997)

1 Introduction

In a previous note [1] the optimum focal length (F) and baselength (B) were derived as functions of the linear pixel width (W). However, no optimisation with respect to W was made, because the quantum efficiency was assumed to be independent of W , and other limitations depending on pixel size were not included. As a consequence the estimated accuracy improved monotonically with decreasing W , which is unrealistic for very small pixels.

In the present note some of the physical effects which become important for small pixels are taken into account, albeit in a very simplistic manner. These include in particular the variation of quantum efficiency (QE) and modulation transfer function (MTF) with pixel size. Although the realism of the detailed assumptions can be disputed, the conclusion is that the various factors tend to compensate each other, so that the variation of astrometric precision is marginal within a rather wide range of pixel sizes. The best choice could therefore well be governed by completely different factors such as price and availability. With this caveat, a pixel size of about $W = 7 \mu\text{m}$ seems reasonable and compatible with a baselength of about $B = 1.5 \text{ m}$ (assuming $F = 40 \text{ m}$).

Compared with the previous note a new calibration of absolute stellar fluxes has been used (cf. [2]) which gives slightly higher count rates for red objects. The error estimates for the same F , B and W are therefore not identical to those given in [1], even in the reference case when the QE and MTF degradations are not included.

2 Pixel size, QE and MTF

Apparently, the QE and MTF of a (front-illuminated) CCD are both directly related to the thickness of the detection zone (the silicon layer in which the photon may be absorbed to produce an electron-hole pair). High QE requires that the detection zone is optically thick, i.e. that the geometrical thickness $z > \alpha^{-1}$, where α is the absorption coefficient. Typical values of α^{-1} for silicon are $2 \mu\text{m}$ at $\lambda 500 \text{ nm}$, $10 \mu\text{m}$ at $\lambda 800 \text{ nm}$ and $100 \mu\text{m}$ at $\lambda 1000 \text{ nm}$ [3]. In the wavelength region of particular interest for GAIA ($\lambda > 700 \text{ nm}$) the detection zone is almost optically thin and the QE is then basically proportional to its geometrical thickness, z .

The loss of MTF is mainly caused by charge diffusion. Because of the low absorptivity in red, most photoelectrons are produced some distance ($\sim z$) below the depletion zone and will reach the voltage well only after diffusion (random walk) by this distance. Depending on the ratio z/W (and also on the diffusion length) there is a certain probability that the charge ends up in the voltage well of an adjacent pixel. This phenomenon is called

charge diffusion or pixel cross talk. Theories exist which predict the MTF degradation as function of the depletion width (or detection depth) and diffusion length; see e.g. [3]. These seem to be difficult to apply in the present case as they depend on material and geometrical parameters which are not known. For this analysis we adopt a simpler view, assuming that the diffusion causes a lateral spread with a characteristic $(1/e)$ width of d ; in this case the MTF loss will be:

$$M_d(f) = \frac{1}{1 + (2\pi fd)^2} \quad (1)$$

where f is the spatial frequency. The factor $M_d(f)$ is readily incorporated in the accuracy analysis, e.g. as an additional factor on $U(w)$ in Equation (31) of [4], with $f = w/F\lambda_0$, provided that d is known. It is not clear how d would depend on z . In one extreme, it could be considered proportional to z ; in another, it could be constant. Both cases will therefore be considered.

Another phenomenon which will reduce the MTF is charge transfer inefficiency. The charge transfer efficiency (CTE) may be written $1 - \epsilon$, where ϵ is a very small number. ϵ is the fraction of charges ‘left behind’ during each transfer (note that two, three or four successive transfers may be required to shift the charges by one pixel). At three times the sampling frequency the reduction in MTF is, theoretically, $\exp(-1.5N_{ct}\epsilon)$ [3], where N_{ct} is the number of charge transfers. This could be a serious limiting factor for very small pixels, since both N_{ct} and (probably) ϵ increase for small W . The effect is however negligible if $\epsilon \sim 10^{-6}$ can be realised. In contrast to the charge diffusion, charge transfer inefficiency causes an asymmetric blurring of the charge pattern, and hence phase errors of importance for the astrometry. Moreover, the phase errors could be magnitude dependent, as the CTE itself may depend on the number of charges transported. Thus, a very good CTE may be necessary also from the viewpoint of possible systematic errors. In the calculations reported below the MTF loss due to the CTE is not included, which is equivalent to assuming $\text{CTE} > 0.999999$.

Finally we should also note the possibility to *improve* the MTF in case a three-phases CCD can be used. By shifting the charges by a third of the pixel width in the time it takes the image to move the same distance, the time window of the TDI is reduced to one third of the width otherwise assumed. In the accuracy analysis [4] this can be included e.g. if the factor $\text{sinc}^2(\pi W f)$ in Equation (31) is replaced by:

$$\text{sinc}(\pi W f) \text{sinc}(\pi W f/3) \quad (2)$$

where, as before, $f = w/F\lambda_0$ is the spatial frequency and $W = F\Delta\xi$ the pixel width.

3 Accuracy calculations

The optimum baselength B_{opt} and the corresponding astrometric accuracy σ_a were computed as functions of pixel width W by including (or, for reference, not including) the effects of QE and charge diffusion, assuming different scaling laws for QE and d versus W . The various cases are described hereafter and the numerical results are summarised in Table 1. In all cases a focal length of $F = 40$ m was assumed. Other assumptions are as in [1].

Case A: Reference

The ‘nominal’ QE curve of Figure 1 in [1] was used for all pixel sizes, and no degradation of MTF due to charge diffusion or CTE was included. Apart from the revised stellar fluxes, the results are equivalent to those in [1].

Case B: Degraded QE

As explained in the Alenia APLT-AMTS report on direct fringe detection [5], Section 4.2.1, the detection layer is normally made no thicker than the pixel width in order to give an acceptable MTF at the Nyquist frequency. For pixels smaller than $10\ \mu\text{m}$ this implies, at least in the long wavelength region, that the detection layer is optically thin in which case the QE is proportional to z , and hence to W . Figure 4-7 in [5] shows that the QE curves do indeed scale more or less linearly with W for pixel sizes between $2.4\ \mu\text{m}$ and $5.1\ \mu\text{m}$. Extrapolating to $W = 10\ \mu\text{m}$ would give a maximum QE of 80% around $\lambda 500\ \text{nm}$, close to the ‘nominal’ curve of case A. (This is probably just a coincidence, as the CCDs are of completely different types.) In case B this effect is included simply by scaling the nominal QE curve by the factor $W/(10\ \mu\text{m})$.

Case C: Degraded QE + charge diffusion with constant d

The Alenia report [5] claims (Section 4.2.9) an MTF of ~ 0.64 at the Nyquist frequency for the Philips CCD with $2.4\ \mu\text{m}$ pixels. Putting $f = 1/2W$ and $M_d = 0.64$ in Equation (1) above gives $d = 0.6\ \mu\text{m}$. Putting this effect on top of case B gives case C.

Case D: Degraded QE + proportional charge diffusion

Since the degraded QE is due to the reduced thickness z , and since the lateral diffusion length d should increase with z , at least in red, a more realistic assumption is perhaps to scale d in proportion to W . Assuming $d = 0.6\ \mu\text{m}$ for $W = 2.4\ \mu\text{m}$ gives the relation $d = 0.25W$, which is assumed in case D. The MTF at two thirds of the Nyquist frequency, where the fringes typically are, is about 0.78 for all pixel sizes.

Case E: High QE + strong diffusion

If one gives up the requirement of a good MTF at the Nyquist frequency, it should in principle be possible to manufacture CCDs with small pixels and high QE. For case F we assume the same QE as in case A, but with a diffusion length of $d = 2.5\ \mu\text{m}$, corresponding to the maximum value in case D (for $W = 10\ \mu\text{m}$). The MTF due to the charge diffusion at two thirds of the Nyquist frequency is, in this case, 0.78 for the $10\ \mu\text{m}$ pixels, decreasing to 0.17 for the smallest pixels.

Case F: Case C + TDI with reduced time window

This is the same as case C but including the modified time sample window according to Equation (2).

Table 1. Optimum baselength (B_{opt}) and astrometric standard error (σ_a) as functions of pixel width (W) for case A to F. The standard errors refer to the parallax of a $V = 15$ mag unreddened K3III star. The corresponding angular errors from one chip crossing (5 cam = 2.15 s) are 27.02 times larger. See [1] for other assumptions.

W [μm]	B_{opt} [m]						σ_a [μas]					
	(A)	(B)	(C)	(D)	(E)	(F)	(A)	(B)	(C)	(D)	(E)	(F)
10.0	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.7	1.2	10.31	10.31	10.40	11.50	11.50	8.95
9.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.7	0.7	1.3	9.74	10.26	10.41	11.59	11.18	8.87
8.0	1.1	1.1	1.1	0.9	0.8	1.4	9.08	10.16	10.34	11.67	10.89	8.80
7.0	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.1	0.9	1.6	8.35	9.99	10.24	11.61	10.57	8.74
6.0	1.5	1.5	1.4	1.2	1.0	1.8	7.59	9.82	10.13	11.42	10.21	8.73
5.0	1.7	1.7	1.6	1.4	1.1	2.0	6.80	9.65	10.07	11.20	9.83	8.77
4.0	2.1	2.1	2.0	1.7	1.2	2.3	5.98	9.51	10.12	10.98	9.45	8.94
3.0	*2.4	*2.4	2.3	2.2	1.3	*2.4	5.15	9.51	10.39	10.83	9.13	9.49
2.4	*2.4	*2.4	*2.4	*2.4	1.4	*2.4	4.78	9.94	10.89	10.89	8.98	10.26

* a limit of $B \leq 2.4$ m was applied

4 Discussion and conclusions

Only in the (unrealistic) case A is there a strong incentive to go to very small pixels. When the additional effects of QE and MTF degradation are included, the accuracy is more or less independent of pixel width. At any rate the variation of σ_a with W is so shallow that the formal minimum depends very strongly on details of the modelling. Thus, the optimisation of W is in practice determined by other factors than those considered here.

Such other factors will most probably favour a relatively large pixel size. Provisionally, we should therefore choose the largest pixel compatible with an acceptable optical configuration. A certain minimum baselength ($B > 1.2$ m) is required for the optical design, and a somewhat longer B will be advantageous for the resolution of binaries. A reasonable compromise could be $W \simeq 7 \mu\text{m}$ and $B \simeq 1.5$ m.

An interesting observation is that the trade-off between QE and MTF is non-trivial, i.e. that a bad MTF (at the Nyquist frequency) may be preferable to a bad QE (cf. cases D and E). Thus the optimum pixel geometry may have a somewhat unconventional depth/width ratio.

The advantage of the three-phase TDI operation is apparent from a comparison of cases C and F. The gain is some 15% in the standard error, while at the same time a 20% larger pixel width can be used with the same baselength (with a corresponding reduction in the data rate).

References

1. L. Lindegren: Optimisation of optics for direct fringe detection,
30 June 1997 (= GAIA_LL_3)
2. L. Lindegren: Which apparent magnitude produces a count rate of 100 Hz?
15 July 1997 (= GAIA_LL_5)
3. G.C. Holst: CCD Arrays, Cameras, and Displays, JCD Publishing, 1996
4. L. Lindegren: Astrometric precision for direct fringe detection (v1),
15 April 1997 (= GAIA_LL_1)
5. APLT-AMTS Direct Fringe Detection, Alenia technical note W.P. 1233
(SE/TNI 127/97)